

Pipelines used to quantify and characterize repeats in the genome and transcriptomes of *Setaria viridis*.

(a) Analysis pipeline for repeats in genome skimming data using RepeatExplorer2. (b) Analysis pipeline for characterizing complete and incomplete LTR retroelements in the whole genome assembly data from Mamidi et al. (2020). Input data and generated data are in orange boxes while the bioinformatic tools used are in yellow boxes.

